

ESTIMATION OF CHROMIUM BY ALKALINE MERCURIC OXIDE.

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It has been found that the trivalent chromium ion is converted into a hexavalent one by the action of alkaline mercuric oxide with the separation of mercury.

Quite a large number of methods have been described in the literature for the oxidation of trivalent Cr^{+++} into a hexavalent one. Action of almost all the well-known oxidising agents has been studied. Even alkaline silver oxide was found by Meneghini (*Gazzetta*, 1912, 42, 1), to oxidise chromic salt solutions to chromates. He represented the reaction by the following equation

But Hans (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 140, 337) and Lyden (*ibid.*, 1937, 234, 59) have subsequently shown that Ag_2O was reduced to metallic silver and no sub-oxide of the type described by Meneghini was formed.

Alkaline mercuric oxide has also been used with success as an oxidising agent in organic chemistry, and methods have been developed for the estimation of reducing sugars and polyhydric alcohols with its help. It was, therefore, considered of some interest to study the action of alkaline mercuric oxide on chromic salt solutions. As a result, it has now been found, as described in the present paper, that chromic salts in solution are completely oxidised to chromate by alkaline mercuric oxide under suitable conditions, thus permitting the estimation of chromium volumetrically in a solution. The method, however, fails in presence of iron. The iron hydroxide precipitate always holds tenaciously quite an appreciable amount of chromium. The reaction proceeds according to the simple equation,

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Procedure.—The solution of chromic salt (chloride, sulphate and nitrate), mixed with the requisite quantity of mercuric chloride solution, was treated with the caustic soda solution. The mixture containing the precipitated mercuric oxide in suspension was boiled for about 13 minutes. The yellow HgO turned black or brown due to the separation of metallic mercury, and the solution became yellow due to the formation of chromate. This was filtered and washed with hot water till free from alkali. Chromium was estimated iodometrically in the filtrate after acidification. The results are incorporated in Table I.

TABLE I.

3G. of HgCl₂ require 0.885 g. NaOH for precipitation as HgO.

HgCl ₂ .	Alkali added.	Chromium		HgCl ₂ .	Alkali added.	Chromium	
		used.	found.			used.	found.
3 g.	1 g.	0.04393 g.	0.002686 g.	0.5 g.	5 g.	0.04125 g.	0.04125 g.
"	2	"	0.04246	"	"	"	0.04125
"	3	"	0.04298	1.0	6	"	0.04125
"	4	"	0.04307	"	"	"	0.04125
"	5	"	0.04316	"	5	"	0.04107
4.5	3	"	0.04263	"	"	"	0.04107
"	5	"	0.04281	1.5	7	"	0.04107
"	7	"	0.04307	"	"	"	0.04107
6	4	"	0.04246 g.	0.75	4	"	0.04090
"	10	"	0.04298	"	"	"	0.04090
"	5	0.04125	0.04119	1.5	9	"	0.04125
				"	"	"	0.04125

From the above results it is clear that about six times or more of alkali by weight compared to that of HgCl₂ is necessary for complete oxidation. Table II gives results of such quantitative reactions.

TABLE II.

1 G. HgCl_2 requires 0.295 g. of NaOH for precipitation as HgO .

HgCl ₂ used.	Alkali used.	Chromium		HgCl ₂ used.	Alkali used.	Chromium	
		added.	found.			added.	found.
0.5 g.	3 g.	0.01161 g.	0.01161 g.	1.5 g.	9 g.	0.03986 g.	0.03986 g.
"	"	0.01161	0.01161	"	"	0.03986	0.03986
"	"	0.01716	0.01716	1.0	6	0.04576	0.04576
"	"	0.01716	0.01716	"	"	0.04576	0.04576
"	"	0.02288	0.02288	0.7	"	0.04783	0.04783
"	"	0.02288	0.02288	"	"	0.04783	0.04783
"	.5	0.03206	0.03206	1.0	"	0.05590	0.05590
"	"	0.03206	0.03206	"	"	0.05590	0.05590

TABLE III.

	Alkali used.	Cr taken.	Cr found.
0.57 G. red HgO	4 g.	0.02288 g.	No reaction.
0.4 G. HgCl_2 precipitated with NaOH and freed from NaOH	3	0.01716	0.01716 g.

The results show that red dry HgO , as available in the market, fails to react even in presence of an excess of alkali, while freshly precipitated HgO is quite active,

TABLE IV.

Cr used in each expt. = 0.05384 g., requires 0.02482 g. O_2 for complete oxidation. NaOH used in each expt. = 5g.

HgCl_2 .	O_2 equiv from HgCl_2 used.	Cr from the chromate.	O_2 equiv. from the chromate formed.
0.207254 g.	0.012232 g.	0.02655 g.	0.01226 g.
0.310881	0.018348	0.03992	0.01841
0.414506	0.024464	0.05232	0.02450
0.466321	0.027522	0.05384	0.02482
0.518135	0.030580	0.05384	0.02482

This table shows that the reaction proceeds according to the simple equation,

and no lower oxide of mercury is formed.

It is interesting to note in this connection that the reverse action, i.e., the oxidation of metallic Hg by chromate in acid solution leads to the formation of mercurous oxide or salts, as has been recently shown by Paris (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1937, 4, 1803).

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